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The Mathematical Miracles of the Holy Qur'an

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Abstract

Quran being a complete code of life encompasses each and every field of life till the Day life ends. Among these fields one of the most important is Mathematics which is being used in every field of modern age. It is astonishing that Mathematics is also present in the Holy Quran and its Mathematical Miracles surprise the people of this modern age era. The Mathematical codes used in the Quran are Prime Numbers in which Code 7 and Code 19 have the Primary position. So Quran being a Divine Book shows Mathematical Miracles when this subject has key position in the advancement of Science and Technology.

Keyword: Mathematics in Quran, Modern age, Code 7, Code 19, Science, Technology

Introduction

The Holy Qur'an is the last book revealed by Allah Almighty and Allah Almighty has taken responsibility of protecting it till the Day of Resurrection and has declared it as an unparalleled and unique book. In it Allah Almighty has accumulated the knowledge of the first and the last people. Calling him a guide and a light, He has also given the glad tidings of success in this world and in the hereafter to those who follow his commands. Just as there is no need for any religion after Islam until the Day of Judgment, there is no need for any other divine book after the Qur'an until the Day of Judgment.

In the "prelim" of Maulana Maududi's book "Fazail e Qur'an" the greatness and universality of the Qur'an is told in these words:

"The Qur'an is great in that no other book in the world can compare with it. It is a miracle in terms of its language and literature as well as a miracle in terms of its teachings and wisdom. At that time man was incapable of making a word like this and he is still incapable today. None of its words have ever been proved wrong and cannot be disproved. Falsehood cannot counter it from the front nor it can be defeated by attacking from behind, and it is so generous that the more a person seeks guidance from him, the more he guides him, and the more he follows him, the more benefits of this world and the hereafter are obtained and passed on. There is no limit to its benefits and profits where man can become absolutely free from it or where ends up its benefiting."¹

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Allah Almighty not only challenges the likeness of this in the Qur'an but also claims that its likeness is impossible:

"فَلَنْ يَجْتَمِعَتِ الْإِنْسُ وَالْجِنُّ عَلَى أَنْ يَأْتُوا بِمِثْلِ هَذَا الْقُرْآنِ لَا يَأْتُونَ بِمِثْلِهِ وَلَوْ كَانَ بَعْضُهُمْ لِبَعْضٍ ظَهِيرًا"²

“Say: If all mankind and the jinn together wish to bring (a book) like the Qur'an, it is not possible for them to be like it, though they may be of one another's helpers.”

In modern times, with the advancement of knowledge and science, innumerable new branches of the tree of knowledge have sprung up in which the role of mathematics has become very important. For a researcher, it has become very important that if the knowledge of the first and last has been added in the Qur'an, so has Allah, the All-Knowing, the All-Wise, included mathematics in it, whereas Allah has already indicated it in the Qur'an al-Hakim

"وَأَحْصَىٰ كُلَّ شَيْءٍ عَدَدًا"³

“And he has counted everything.”

It may come as a surprise to a researcher that mathematics is also present in the Qur'an because apparently there are a few numbers in the Qur'an but in fact the Qur'an has everything from very simple numbers to complex mathematical operations.

Definition and Importance of Mathematics

“Mathematics is actually the study of the properties of quantities and the relationship between them through the use of numbers. It also discusses structures, shapes and transformations. It is likely that knowledge about the origin or evolution actually count, count to, measurement and the basic factors to study objects shapes and motions of abstraction and logical reasoning.”⁴

Mathematics is the common language and basic tool of all sciences. Mathematics has always influenced philosophers throughout history. With the focus on mathematical approaches, the scientific field has greatly improved. All the amazing technologies of modern times, even cars, trains, satellites, medicines, means of communication (telephone, mobile), etc., came into being by use of mathematics. Without the use of mathematics, we would not have been able to understand the universe and there would have been no new inventions. Mathematics has become very important in the last four centuries. Today's modern scientific logic is because of the use of mathematics. According to Galileo, who played a key role in giving mathematics a fundamental role, mathematics is the language in which God wrote the universe. The use of mathematics is the greatest in all fields of life. If the universe is described in the language of mathematics, then we should not be surprised that God's book also uses the language of mathematics. In the time of Prophet Moses, magic was at its peak, so Allah Almighty gave miracles according to that age which turned magicians into monotheists. Similarly, the Qur'an has described its mathematical miracles at a time when science and its language "mathematics" are at their peak.⁵

With the development of various sciences, new unique scientific and mathematical miracles of the Holy Qur'an are emerging which stun the intellect. In fact, the whole universe is dependent on calculations, which are based on some strange units that have no room for change. So far, 92 different elements have been discovered in the universe, each with different characteristics and status. Each has a different atomic

number and weight, but the number of atoms in the atomic gram number of each element is always 6.24×10^{23} constant. Similarly, the law of gravity is the same all over the universe. If even a small difference were made, the existence of stars, planets and the universe would be impossible. If the force of gravity were reduced, then all the cosmic bodies would spread out like gas balls and disappear, and if there were even a little more, the universe in its earliest days would have become a very solid shell and would have collapsed on its own.⁶

The Beginning of the Discovery of the Holy Quran on the Computer

The miracle of composing and arranging the Holy Quran on a computer began with the research of Rashid Khalifa, an Egyptian chemist who settled in the United States in the 1960s. In 1968, Rashid Khalifa based on his hobby uploaded all the letters, words and verses of the Holy Quran to computer and started looking for a connection between them. Gradually more people joined the research and by 1976 it had taken the form of a regular school. During this time, researchers discovered that the order of the Qur'anic letters, words, verses and surahs is based on a special miraculous calculation and according to their research, the number 19 is fundamental. Rashid Khalifa and his colleagues wrote many books and papers on the system of arithmetic but unfortunately Rashid Khalifa fell prey to satanic whispers and claimed to be the last prophet and in 1990 died as pagan.⁷

The Miraculous Choice of Words of the Qur'an

First of all, the miracles of the Qur'an are described which one does not have to work hard to understand. Anyone can easily understand these common sense things:

*The word "day" is used 365 times in the Qur'an.⁸ Number 365 not only shows the number of days in the calendar but also the relationship between the world and the sun. When the earth completes one revolution around the sun, it revolves around its own axis 365 times. In other words, when the earth completes one of its cycles around the sun, it means that we have lived on earth for 365 days. It is important to note that the word "day" is used 365 times in the Qur'an because the earth completes one revolution around the sun in 365 days.

The plural of days "youm" or "ayyam" is used 30 times and represents the number of days in a month.⁹

The number of months in the sight of Allah is 12. The word "shahr" which means month is used 12 times in the Qur'an which is equal to the number of months in a year.¹⁰

In the Qur'an, "day" is used 365 times while its plural is used 30 times and all the words derived from day are used $475 = 19 \times 25$ times. Like 19, number 25 is also a very important number. Like the earth, the sun revolves around its own axis. The earth revolves 365 times and the sun 25 times.¹¹

The word "day" alone is a mathematical miracle. Out of all the 475 derivative of the day, *يَوْمَانِ* (that day) is used for the end of the world, while *يوم القيامة* is used in the sense of resurrection. Both are used equally 70 times.¹²

*In the Qur'an, the word "Al Qamar" means the moon appears 27 times. This is the period during which the moon completes its orbit around the earth. A lunar month has 29 days. The main reason for this difference is that when the moon revolves around

the earth, the earth also revolves around the sun, due to which the moon completes its rotation around the earth after two days delay.¹³

*The word “world” has been mentioned 115 times in the Qur'an and the word “Hereafter” has also been used 115 times.

*In the Qur'an, the Almighty says that we have created seven heavens. It is noteworthy that the verses containing “seven heavens” also appear seven times in the entire Qur'an.¹⁴

* “Desire” and “Fear” come equally 8 times in the Holy Quran.

* Muhammad ﷺ and Shari'ah (his ﷺ teachings) have come 4 times each.¹⁵

*In the Qur'an, the word “man” is used 23 times and the word “woman” is also used 23 times. According to modern science, a child takes 23 chromosomes from the mother's egg and 23 from the father's germ. So the Quran has accumulated person even on the basis of chromosomes.¹⁶

*Where the word “Paradise” is used 77 times in the Qur'an, “Hell” is also mentioned 77 times.

*In the Qur'an, the contradictory words of “Faith and “Disbelief” have been used exact 25 times each.¹⁷

*There is ease with every difficulty. In the Qur'an, the word “Alyasar” is used for ease and “Al-Usr” for difficulty. Both have been mentioned 36 times.

*“Jihad” is the spirit of Islam. This word is used 41 times in the Qur'an. Similarly, the word “Muslims” has appeared 41 times, which attracts Muslims to jihad.¹⁸

* “Abrar” which means righteous and “Fajjr” which means wicked, are relatively mentioned in the Qur'an. The word Abrar has been mentioned 6 times while Fajr has been mentioned 3 times, which means that the chances of becoming Abrar among the people are twice as high as Fajjr.

*The words of “Reward” and “Forgiveness” also appear in the Qur'an in relative terms. Reward, which means retribution, is mentioned 117 times in the Qur'an, while forgiveness, which is one of the highest blessings of the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful, is mentioned 234 times.¹⁹

*Giving thanks increases blessings while ungratefulness causes trouble. The word “Thankfulness” has been mentioned 77 times and the “Trouble” for ungratefulness has also been mentioned 77 times.

* “Life” and “Death” are with human beings. These words are used 145 times in the Qur'an for both.

* Both “Vision” and “Insight” are mentioned 148 times.²⁰

*The word “Angels” is mentioned 88 times in the Holy Qur'an while the name of their opponent “Satan” is also mentioned 88 times.

*The word “Alcohol” has been mentioned 6 times and its effect “Sakara” has also been mentioned 6 times.²¹

*In the Qur'an, "Iblis" has been declared the greatest and open enemy of humanity, so Muslims should seek "Refuge" from the evil of Satan. Both words are used 11 times in the Qur'an.

*The word "Bir" (goodness) and all its derivatives are mentioned 20 times. We will reap what we sow in the next world. No good will remain unrewarded. The word "Reward" and all its derivatives are also mentioned 20 times.²²

*In the Qur'an, Jesus is called like Adam because both were born without a father. The name of "Jesus" has been mentioned 25 times in the Holy Qur'an and the name of "Adam" has also been mentioned 25 times.

*The word "Qul (قل)" means Say has been used 332 times, while the word "Qalu (قالو)" means They Said has been repeated 332 times.²³

*The "World" is the place of action while the "Hereafter" is the place of reward. Both have been mentioned 115 times.

* "Faith" and "Disbelief" have been brought together 25 times.

"Paradise" is the place of God's pleasure and blessings, while "Hell" is the place of God's wrath and torment. Both have been mentioned 77 times.²⁴

*The word "Profit" meaning benefit and its opposite "Loss" meaning disadvantage both have been brought equally 50 times.

*The word "Salaat" ie prayers has come 5 times and only 5 prayers in a day and night are obligatory on Muslims.

* "Al-Insan" means human being has come 65 times while the stages of human formation has also come 65 times. (Turab 17 times +Nutfa 12 times + Alaq 6 times + Muzgha 3 times +Ezaam 15+ Laham 12 times = 65 times)²⁵

Quran and the Prime Numbers

In the previous section, mathematical miracles of the Qur'an are described which are easy to understand but impossible to imitate. You don't have to be a mathematician to understand them, but anyone who knows how to count and can count numbers can easily understand these miracles. In this section, miracles are described with reference to the prime numbers of the Qur'an, which show the impossibility of copying the Qur'an, its fabrication beyond human capacity and complete protection from human interference. Prime Numbers (Prime number is that which is divided by "1" or by itself. It can't be divided by any other digit.)²⁶ have a special significance in the mathematical miracle of the Holy Qur'an, of which 7 and 19 are prime numbers of utmost importance.

Allah Almighty revealed the Qur'an in Arabic with 28 (7*4) alphabets.

The Qur'an begins with Surah Al-Fatiha which consists of 7 verses and surprisingly only 21 (7*3) letters out of 28 Arabic letters are used in Surah Al-Fatiha.²⁷ Surah Al-Fatiha contains 7 verses, 29 words and 139 letters that are all prime numbers and the sum of these numbers (7=7, 2+9=11, 1+3+9=13) is also the prime numbers. Now if the numbers obtained from the addition of these numbers are added, we get 7+11+13=31 which is another prime number and if these added prime numbers are again added from left to right (7+2+9+1+3+9=31) and right to left (139297=1+3+9+2+9+7= 31) then we obtain 31.²⁸

After believing that Surah Al-Fatihah consists of prime numbers, the question arises as to whether the complete structure of the Qur'an consists of prime numbers which consists of 114 Surahs and 6236 verses ($7+286+200+176+120+\dots+4+5+6=6236$) which are not prime numbers.

Although the number of Surahs (114) and Total Verses (6236) are not prime numbers, the verse of Surah Al-Hijr of the Qur'an **وَلَقَدْ آتَيْنَاكَ سَبْعًا مِّنَ الْمَثَانِي وَالْفُرْآنَ وَالْعَظِيمِ**²⁹ (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) made it clear that "سبعاً مثنى" means Surah Al-Fatihah.

Thus when we divide the Qur'an into two parts (i) Surah Al-Fatihah which is the key chapter and (ii) the rest of the Qur'an in which the rest of the message is given which consists of 113 Suras then 114 Suras and 6236 verses are completely divided into prime numbers:

Quran	Fatiha	Message
114	1	113
6236	7	6229

All 7, 113 and 6229 are prime numbers and the sum of their digits ($3+1+1=5$, $7=7$, $9+2+2+6=19$) are also prime numbers. 1 is the purest prime number and really indivisible. Therefore, it is considered a unit.³⁰

The verse **الْأَلِفِ الْبَاءِ الْهَاءِ رَبُّكُمْ تَكْدِبَانِ** of Surah Ar-Rahman has been repeated 31 times and 31 is a prime number. Add the verse number where this verse is repeated, i.e.

$13+16+18+21+23+25+28+30+32+34+36+38+40+42+45+47+49+51+53+55+57+59+61+63+65+67+69+71+73+75+77=1433$ is obtained which is itself a Prime Number.³¹

Another thing to note is that the remaining 47 verses ($78-31=47$) is also another prime number and its addition $4+7=11$ is also a prime number. The alphabetical value of this verse is 683 which is a prime number and $6+8+3=17$ is also a prime number.³²

The Miracles of Code 7

Keep in mind that there is a mathematical connection in all the sets of natural numbers of the Qur'an and this connection is code 7 and code 19. The number of Initial Letters used in the beginning of 29 Suras in the Qur'an is also 14 ($7*2$) and the interesting thing is that in the composition of these 14 letter segments, if the recurring letters are removed, then a total of 14 letters are used which are as follows

And the numerical value of these letters is: **ا، ه، ر، س، ص، ت، ع، ق، ك، ل، م، ن، ح اور ی۔**
 1, 6, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 28 and the sum of which gives 247 and $247 = (19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19 + 19)$.

This proves that all the letters are encoded by code 19.

The sum of the first two digits is $1+6=7$ and the sum of the first seven digits is also 77 which is a multiple of 7. This proves that the mathematical miracle of the Qur'an is based on code 7 and code 19.³³

Number 7 is also a very important Prime Number. This number seems to be closely related to the formation and way of formation of our universe. The Earth has seven

layers which are crust, lithosphere, upper mantle, steno sphere, lower mantle, outer core and inner core. The basic building blocks of matter, the atoms, are made up of seven layers. There are seven heavens in the universe. The night sky, we see, is just one of these seven.

The number of verses in the Qur'an which point to the seven heavens is seven.

The word "hereafter" is mentioned 70 times in the Qur'an, which is a multiple of 7.

Hell has 7 gates and the word "hell" is repeated 77 times in the Qur'an which is a multiple of 7.³⁴

The air in which we breathe is made up of 78% of nitrogen in its molecular state, which consists of 7 protons, 7 neutrons, and 7 electrons. The number of colors in the spectrum of light is also 7.³⁵

During Hajj, Muslims perform Tawaf around the Kaaba 7 times. "Sa'I" is also performed 7 times between Safa and Marwa.

Verse 196 of Surah Al-Baqarah mentions 7 days and 196 is also a multiple of 7. ($196=4*7*7$).³⁶

The first time Allah Almighty mentions No.7 in Surah Al Baqara No.2 verse No. 29 and the last time He mentions it in Surah Al Naba No.78 verse No.12. Now

(i) There are 77 Surahs between the first Surah No. 2 and the last Surah No. 78 which describes this number, which is a multiple of 7.

(ii) Surprisingly, there are 5649 verses between the first verse and the second verse which describes the number 7, which is a multiple of 7.

(iii) Even more astonishing is the number of verses which are mentioned from the beginning of Surah No.2 to the verse where No.7 is mentioned for the first time. The number of verses is the same as from the verse which mentions No.7 last time in Surah 78. 28 verses are mentioned which is a multiple of 7.

(iv) Further more from the beginning of Surah No.2 which mentions No.7 for the first time, to Surah No.78 which mentions No.7 for the last time, there are a total of 5705 verses which is a multiple of 7.

(v) There are a total of 35 verses before the verse describing No.7 for the first time, which is a multiple of 7.

(vi). There are a total of 5684 verses before the verse describing No.7 for the last time, which is a multiple of seven.³⁷

Discovery and Miracles of Code 19

After describing some of the miracles of the number 7 in this section we will describe some of the miracles of the number 19. The number 19 is also a very important prime number. The Allah Almighty has claimed that the Qur'an is unique and unparalleled, as stated:

"وَمَا كَانَ هَذَا الْقُرْآنُ أَنْ يُفْتَرَى مِنْ دُونِ اللَّهِ وَلَكِنْ تَصْدِيقَ الَّذِي بَيْنَ يَدَيْهِ وَتَفْصِيلَ الْكِتَابِ لَا رَيْبَ فِيهِ مِنْ رَبِّ الْعَالَمِينَ 0 أَمْ يَقُولُونَ افْتَرَاهُ قُلْ فَأْتُوا بِسُورَةٍ مِثْلِهِ وَادْعُوا مَنِ اسْتَلَطَعْتُمْ مِنْ دُونِ اللَّهِ إِنْ كُنْتُمْ صَادِقِينَ"³⁸

“And it is not a Quran that has been forged without Allah's revelation, but it is a confirmation of what was revealed before it and of the Book. There is no doubt that it is from the Lord of the worlds. Do they say that you have fabricated it? Say: Then bring a single surah like it. And call upon those whom you can besides Allah, if you are truthful.”

And the mathematical sequence has a big hand in making it unique. The number 19 has a special significance in the mathematical sequence of the Qur'an and this number is about the nineteen angels who supervise hell in verse 30 of Surah Mudassir. ³⁹ عَلَّمَهَا (And there are nineteen (angels appointed) on it (Hell). That is, Allah Almighty has chosen the number 19 for monitoring.

The number 19 is a proof that the structure of the Qur'an is miraculous. In addition, Allah draws attention to the number 19 in the Qur'an to strengthen the faith of those who believe.

"(وَمَا جَعَلْنَا أَصْحَابَ النَّارِ إِلَّا مَلَائِكَةً وَمَا جَعَلْنَا عِدَّتَهُمْ إِلَّا فِتْنَةً لِلَّذِينَ كَفَرُوا لِيَسْتَيَقِنَ الَّذِينَ أُوتُوا الْكِتَابَ وَيَزِدَّ الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا إِيمَانًا وَلَا يَرْتَابَ الَّذِينَ أُوتُوا الْكِتَابَ وَالْمُؤْمِنُونَ وَلِيَقُولَ الَّذِينَ فِي قُلُوبِهِم مَّرَضٌ وَالْكَافِرُونَ مَاذَا أَرَادَ اللَّهُ بِهَذَا مَثَلًا"⁴⁰

“And We have appointed guardians of the Fire only as angels, and We have appointed them as a trial for those who disbelieve, so that the people of the Book may believe, and the faith of the believers may increase, and the People of the Book and the believers may not doubt. And the people and the disbelievers say, “What is the meaning of this statement of Allah?”

Discovery of the number 19

Code 19 first gained attention in 1974. Philosophers then saw many more miraculous patterns. Surah No.74 which shows the code of 19 is "Al-Muddaththir" and if 19 is added to 74 then it becomes 1974 which is the year of discovery of the miracles of the number 19 and according to the Islamic calendar it becomes 1393 AH. As the Islamic Calendar starts from migration to Madinah and since Allah Almighty started revealing the Holy Qur'an to him ﷺ 13 years before the migration to Madinah. In other words, this miracle appeared 1406 years after the revelation of the Qur'an, which becomes 1406 (19*74).

The first two verses of this surah are "يَا أَيُّهَا الْمُدَّثِّرُ ۗ قُمْ فَأَنْذِرْ". In the first verse he ﷺ is called “Mudassar” and in the second verse he ﷺ is commanded to stand up and warn the people (out of fear of Allah). These two verses consist of 19 letters and the alphabetical value of these two verses is 1974. If the first verse of Surah Al-Muddaththir is written as 74: 1, it is very interesting that from this verse to the end of the Qur'an, 741 verses become total and 741 = 19*39.⁴¹

The verse that the Qur'an is "سَأَصْبِيهِ سَقَرًا"⁴² warns those who say "إِنْ هَذَا إِلَّا قَوْلُ الْبَشَرِ"⁴³ written by human beings, he will be inserted in “Saqr” and then asked in verse 27 Do you know what Saqr is? Saqr is either Hell or Code 19 which punishes the disbelievers for their deeds and protects the Qur'an which reveals miracles through mathematical system. The word “Saqr” is very important in the miracle of the number 19. “Saqr” is used 4 times throughout the Qur'an and 3 times in Surah “Mudassir” which is mathematically used in the code. The word “Saqr” appears in verses 26, 27 and 42 which add up to 95 (19*5) and the alphabetical value of these verses is 1900

which is equal to 19×100 . If we add Surah No.74 in this alphabetical value then 1974 is obtained which is the year of discovery of the miracle of Code 19.⁴⁴

It is to be noted here that verse no.31 of Surah Mudassir in which the functions of no.19 are told contain 57 (19×3) words.

Verse 31 contains the words 38 (19×2) describing the functions of 19.

The first 19 verses of Surah Mudassir also contain 57 (19×3) words.

Surah Mudassir consists of 95 (19×5) words from beginning to verse number 31.

There are 57 (19×3) verses in Surah Mudassir including Bismillah Ar-Rahman Ar-Rahim.⁴⁵

The Qur'an contains 30 different complete numbers without repeating the same numbers, which are as follows.

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 19, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 99, 100, 200, 300, 1000, 2000, 3000, 5000, 50000, 100000 = 162,146 which is a factor of 19. $162,146 = 8534 \times 19$

In addition to these 30 complete numbers, the Qur'an also mentions 8 fractions:

$1/10, 1/8, 1/6, 1/5, 1/4, 1/3, 1/2, 2/3$. Thus, a total of 38 (19×2) different numbers are mentioned in the Qur'an.⁴⁶

The basic principle of the number 19 is hidden in the first verse of the Book of God, **بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ** which has 19 letters. Therefore, the number 19 is also fundamental in the structure of the Holy Qur'an.⁴⁷

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ is a combination of four words. And these four words have been mentioned "Ism" 19 (19×1) times, "Allah" 2698 (19×142) times, "Ar-Rahman" 57 (19×3) times and "Al-Raheem" 114 (19×6) times throughout the Qur'an.⁴⁸

Similarly, the attributive names also correspond to **بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ** as well. As the word "Wahid" is mentioned 19 times like "Ism" is mentioned 19 times, "Zul-Fazl-ul-Azeem" 2698 times as "Allah" 2698 times, "Majeed" 57 times and "Al-Rahman" 57 times and "Jam'I" 114 times like "Al-Raheem" 114 times.⁴⁹

Except for Surah At-Tawbah, all the surahs of the Qur'an al-Hakim begin with **بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ** which is the beginning of 113 surahs, but in verse 30 of Surah An-Naml 27, with reference to the letter of Hazrat Sulaiman, the whole **بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ** is written in full by which the code of 19 has been ⁵⁰"**إِنَّهُ مِنْ سُلَيْمَانَ وَإِنَّهُ بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ**" completed by fulfilling the shortcoming of Surah At-Tawbah $19 \times 6 = 114$.

There is also a subtle point in this that Surah Tawbah is located at No.9 (9×1) and Surah An-Naml at 27 (9×3) in which **بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ** appears twice. If numbers are added between these two suras, ie:

$(9+10+11+12+13+14+15+16+17+18+19+20+21+22+23+24+25+26+27)=342$ which is exactly the multiple of 19 that is $19 \times 6 \times 3 = 342$. Furthermore, $114 \times 3 = 342$ is also the multiple of the total Surahs of the Qur'an.⁵¹

Even more astonishing is the distance of 342 words between the first **بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ** and the second **بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ** of Surah An-Naml, which is a perfect multiple of 19.⁵² From Surah At-Tawbah, which does not begin with

Bismillah, to Surah An-Naml, there are a total of 19 Surahs in between. When we add Surah No. 27 and its verse No. 30 in which the whole $\text{بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ}$ is repeated, we get $27+30=57$ ($19*3$).⁵³

The first revelation $\text{اقْرَأْ بِاسْمِ رَبِّكَ الَّذِي خَلَقَ}$ contains 19 words and 76 ($19*4$) letters which is a multiple of 19 and he ﷺ was appointed as prophet at the age of 40 and relation of 40 with 4 is clear.

It is also a miracle of the Qur'an that in Surah 96, the first 5 verses of which were revealed in the first revelation, contains total 19 verses.

The total number of letters in Surah Al-Alaq, which is on No.96, is 304 which is a multiple of 19. ($4*4*19=304$)⁵⁴

The second revelation of Surah Al-Qalam has 38 words ($19*2$). In the third revelation, ten verses of Surah Muzammil were revealed with 57 words ($19*3$) and Surah Muddaththir was revealed as the fourth revelation which has a total of 19 verses and the word "Islam" has been mentioned only 19 times in the Qur'an.⁵⁵

The last Surah Al-Nasr of the Qur'an also contains 19 words. The first verse of Surah Al-Nasr which mentions the help of Allah consists of 19 letters.⁵⁶

Miracle of Initial Letters (According to Code 19)

The 29 Suras of the Qur'an begin with words whose meanings are not clear, such as "الم" and "حم", etc., which either contain special allusions or have the names of the Prophet, such as "Yasin" and "Taha", etc. The presumption about "Qaf" is that it is an abbreviation of the Qur'an al-Hakim.⁵⁷

These letters, which appear at the beginning of the 29 Suras of the Qur'an al-Hakim, are a mystery. There are 14 of them, which are half of the Arabic letters and are written in the form of 14 compounds. Computer analysis proves that this is the eternal miracle of the Qur'anic system of arithmetic.

If we combine the letters of 14 initial letters, their fourteen compounds and the number of 29 Suras which begin with these initial letters, then $14+14+29 = 57$ is obtained which is a product of 19. If we add the numbers of Suras which start with initial letters, for example, $(2+3+7+\dots+50+68)$ then 822 is obtained, in which if you add 14 initial letters, then 836 is obtained which is the product of 19. ($19*44=836$)⁵⁸

Even more subtle is that between the first Sura number 2 which starts with initial letters and the last sura number 68, are 38 non-initial letter Suras which are a multiple by 19. ($19*2=38$). The first Sura with initial letters Surah No. 2 of Al-Baqarah and last Surah No. 69 there are total of 5263 ($19*277$) verses between them.⁵⁹

In 29 Suras of the Qur'an, 14 Arabic letters have been used as initial letters. If we add the Numeric Value of these 14 letters ie (a=1, ba =2, ta =3... ..ya =28) then we get 247 which is the product of 19 ($19*13=247$).⁶⁰

The first verse of Surah "Qaf", in which Qaf is used as initial letter, is followed by والقرآن المجيد about which the scholars think that this Qaf is used as an abbreviation for the Qur'an. The number of letters "Qaf" in it is 57 ($19*3$) and Surah "Al-Shura" which starts with "Ha MimAyn Sin Qaf" in which "Qaf" is present in the initial letter and although Surah Al-Shura is twice as big as Surah Qaf, the number of Qaf is only

57 (19*3). Now if we add the number of the letter “Qaf” in Surah Ash-Shura and Surah Qaf which refers to the Holy Qur'an, we get $57+57=114$ (19*6) which is equal to the total number of Surahs of the Qur'an and also بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ appears 114 times in the Qur'an Al-Hakim which also has 19 letters.⁶¹

The 50th Surah which begins with the letter "Qaf" consists of a total of 57 (19*3) Qaf's. The letter “Qaf” is also used in the initial letter of the 42nd Surah Ash-Shura. The total number of Q in it is also 57 (19*3). There are 45 verses in the 50th Surah and if we add Sura no. and verses of this Sura then it makes 95 (19*5). Similarly, in the 42nd Sura, there are a total of 53 verses and in the same way Sura no. and verses of this Sura surprisingly make no.95 (19*5). The alphabetical value of the word “majeed” used for the Qur'an in the first verse of sura "Qaf" is also 57 (19*3). The total number of "Qaf" in the Qur'an is 798 (19*42).⁶²

The letter “Qaf” is the 19th letter in the Arabic alphabet. Another miracle that has been discovered about the letter "Qaf" is that the sum of all the "Qaf's" in the 19th verse of every surah of the Qur'an is 76 (19*4).⁶³

The letter “Nun” appears in Surah No. 68 as an initial letter. In this Surah, the letter “Nun” appears a total of 133 (19*7) times.

When we collect the verses of Surahs multiplied by 19 (ie, total verses 99 of Surah 19, total verses 89 of Surah 38, total verses 30 of Surah 57, total 32 verses of Surah 76, total verses 9 of Surah 95 and Total verses 7 of Surah 114) then total verses become 266 (19*14).⁶⁴

The letter “Sad” is also used as an initial letter in Surah Al A'raf, Surah Maryam and Surah “Sad”, in which the number of letters “Sad” is 97, 26 and 29 respectively. Adding them gives 152 (19*8).

If the letter “Sad” is counted in Surah Al-A'raf in some versions of the Qur'an, then this number becomes 98 instead of 97, which is due to the fact that in some versions, in verse no.69 ⁶⁵ وَالَّذِينَ كَفَرُوا فَذُكِّرُوا آيَةً فَالْحَقُّ بِسِطَّةٍ فَادْكُرُوا آيَةَ اللَّهِ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَفْلِحُونَ" وَزَادَكُمْ فِي" the word بِسِطَّةٍ is spelled from بِصِطَّةٍ. Therefore, some people claim that in this verse, بِسِطَّةٍ is written with “Sad”, but it should be read as “Sin”. To correct this mistake, one of the earliest versions of the Qur'an, “Tashkent”, was used which prove that the word is with the letter “Sin” which indicates that one of the manuscripts mistakenly wrote the letter “Sad” instead of the letter “Sin”. This correction would also prove that Code 19 not only finds the smallest human error in the Qur'an but also corrects it.⁶⁶

In the three Surahs of the Qur'an, Surah Maryam 19, Surah Sad 38 and Surah Al-A'raf 7, the letters “Sad” is present and the total number of “Sad” in these three Surahs is 152 (19*8).

Ha Mim: The two-letter “Ha Mim” appears at the beginning of 40 to 46 of the seven Surahs of the Qur'an and the total number of “Ha” and “Mim” in them is 2147 which is a multiple of 19 ie $19*113=2147$.⁶⁷

Ya Sin: Surah Yaseen is the 36th surah of the Qur'an which contains two initial letters Ya and Sin. Throughout this surah, the letter “Ya” is repeated 237 times and the letter “Sin” 48 times, the sum of which is $237+48=285$ and this is the multiple of 19 ($19*15=285$).⁶⁸

Ayn Sin Qaf: "Ayn Sin and Qaf" are used in Surah No. 42 Al-Shura, the number of which is 98, 54, 57 respectively and their total is 209 which is the multiple of 19. ($19 \times 11 = 209$).⁶⁹

The seventh Surah Al-A'raf starts with the initial letters "Alif Lam Min Sad". In this Surah total Alif 2529+ Lam 1530+ Mim 1164 + and Sad 97 times have been mentioned, the total of which is 5320 (19×280).

The letters "Kaf Ha YaAyn Sad" appear only in one 19th Surah. In this surah, Kaf appears 137 times, Ha 175 times, Ya 343 times, Ayn 117 times and Sad 26 times. The total number of these five letters is 798 (19×42).⁷⁰

Given the importance of the number 19, scholars believe that it is a combination of the numbers 1 and 9, which, in addition to being the beginning and end of the number, add up to 10, $9 + 1 = 10$, which if added further, 1 is obtained ($0+1=1$), that is, the number 19 has a monotheistic character.

This number is also very important in biological and astronomical systems:

The total number of bones in each human being is 209 which is the multiple of 19 ($19 \times 11 = 209$).

The baby stays in the mother's womb for 266 days or 38 months, which is a multiple of 19 ($19 \times 14 = 266$) and ($19 \times 2 = 38$).⁷¹

Earth, moon and sun are important celestial bodies for man and these three come in a straight line in front of each other after 19 years.

The famous asteroid Hally Comet appears every 76 years, which is multiple by 19. ($19 \times 4 = 76$).⁷²

Conclusion

Quran is not a book of Science or Mathematics. It is a complete code of life descended by Allah Almighty yet it comprises all knowledge and subjects till the Adam a.s to the Day of Resurrection. Every human being from any walk of field reads this book and it surprises them all because it gives guidance of all fields. Mathematics is also a field which consists of numbers and in the Quran no one guesses that it also has mathematic from simple to a complex level. When the scientists put the Quran on computer, they surprised that it aslo has mathematics. So in this very short article it is tried to show one of the other aspect which we can say a marvelous Miracle of the Quran, The Mathematical Miracles of the Holy Quran.

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